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Permanent Book-Tax Difference and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the permanent book-tax difference and corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. To achieve this, the study employed an *ex-post facto* research design. The study sourced data from the published audited annual financial statements and annual reports of the selected listed financial firms in Nigeria, covering the forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of that 31 December 2022. The employed descriptive statistics and panel data regression techniques in data analyses. Importantly, the study did not neglect statistical and diagnostic tests. Following the findings of the study, it was possible to conclude that the Permanent Book-Tax Difference (PBD) is significant predictor of corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The results also affirmed that PBD have a negative significant effect on corporate investment expenditure which implies that corporate investment expenditure decreases as this indicator increases. From the results, there is clear evidence to conclude that the results show that PBD does not affect corporate investment expenditure significantly. The study recommends that PBD should be monitored to ensure that the Gap does not widen significantly. Albeit insignificant the negative direction of the effect is a cause for concerns which must be mitigated by effective tax planning policies.

Keywords: Corporate investment expenditure, Firm age, Financial leverage, Operating cash flow, Permanent book-tax difference

INTRODUCTION

The government levies taxes and creates a regulatory and legal framework in which companies can thrive. Businesses, like the government, require additional funding to expand, boost shareholder wealth, and maintain their position as going concerns (Olufemi & Olori, 2022). The researchers found that companies view tax payments as an expense, burden, or cost that cut into their profit margins and liquidity, which in turn lowers their value. Therefore, managers invent and employ all sorts of acceptable cost reduction measures to decrease or at least optimize their tax burden especially if the option of transferring liability exists. Although the words are used interchangeably in the accounting literature, this activity has been characterised as tax sheltering, planning, avoidance, aggression, or reduction in recent studies (Ogbeide & Iyafekhe, 2018 in Delgado et al., 2023). However, McClure et al. (2016) averred that these phrases may have distinct legal or economic connotations. The book-tax difference is the entire gap between the

accounting income and taxable income (Kim et al., 2011, Oyeleke et al., 2016; Demere et al., 2017; Fagbemi et al., 2019; Oeta et al., 2019; Karami et al. 2020).

The financial firms are always seeking capital for investment expenditure to cope with their rapid changing business environment. Currently, we are during rapid evolution in information technology where the survivability of any financial institution in this current hyper-competitive and highly dynamic business environment depends on the effective engagement of diverse resourceful electronic devices to support its service delivery (Olusola, 2014). Investment expenditure needs the acquisition of new assets and upkeep and improvement of existing ones to survive the test of time. Some spending categories which are put aside for investment upkeep are depreciation and amortization. While capital investment expenditure covers the cost of purchase of property, plant and equipment, the cost of acquisition of software or another tangible asset and so on. The lengthy age debate on these practices which skewed towards an area that magnifies tax structures against tax planning actors and sheltering tactics in the accounting and finance research. The proponents thought that these are tactics launched to rub the government off the revenue essential to run the economy. However, the opponents admonished tax and accounting experts to examine theoretical possibilities from other fields. They stated that part of the role of managers is to use their cognitive skills and personal inclinations to save money for the firm within the bounds of the law. Given that the marginal costs of managing taxes by way of time, effort and reputation are primarily incurred by managers they will naturally align with the legal standards. Resultantly, a considerable corpus of tax accounting literature has arisen, over the last decades. Most of this research have focused heavily on the non-financial sector like manufacturing enterprises. There is a scarcity of empirical evidence from the financial sector which is one of the motors of the economy. Against this background, the study set to examine book-tax difference and corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Permanent Book-Tax Difference (PBSD)

The permanent book-tax difference, developed by Manzon et al (2002) and supported by Desai and Dharmapala (2006), is primarily estimated using financial statement data and focuses on the amount of the discrepancy between accounting income and taxable income. It is the most complete metric, capturing both temporary and PBSD. Although the causes of PBSD vary and are typically classified as permanent or temporary discrepancies, the size of the gap reflects the prevalence of tax evasion strategies (Kim et al., 2011). According to Rego (2003), tax-aggressive operations can result in book-tax disparities, which are temporary or permanent discrepancies between a company's financial accounting and taxable revenue. As a result, the numerator is based on taxable income, while the denominator is based on financial accounting income to adjust for PBSD. The PBSD is also used as a proxy for measuring tax evasion behaviour. Several studies have suggested that book-tax disparities can be used as a signal for tax planning (Mills, 1998; Badertscher et al., 2010). Though the total PBSD measure appears simple to calculate, it is prone to measurement errors due to multiple challenges in estimating taxable income from financial statements (Hanlon, 2003). One major impediment to calculating overall book-to-tax discrepancy is the paucity of taxable income in public data (Lee et al., 2015). Other sources of inaccuracy include differences in consolidation rules for book and tax purposes, overseas operations, tax credits, and loss firms, among other things. The study calculated book-tax difference as follows:

$$\text{Book Tax Difference} = \text{Profit Before Tax} - \frac{\text{Tax Expenses}}{\text{Statutory Tax Rate}}$$

Thus, hypothesis was formulated as: H_{01} : *Book-tax difference has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure.*

Corporate Investment Expenditure

According to Helpman et al. (2004), corporations participate in investments for a variety of reasons, including the importance of maintaining corporate control, firm development and wealth growth, trade

friction, and job creation. According to Osegbue et al. (2021), business investment is the allocation of funds with the expectation of a future benefit. They believe that the influx of capital investments is influenced by a variety of factors such as taxation, legal and regulatory frameworks, and the degree of openness, among others. Corporate investment, according to them, is a driver of technological innovation, infrastructural development, wealth creation, employment and empowerment, and a rise in people's standard of living and social well-being in an economy. Consistent with this notion, Adegbite and Shittu (2017) found that corporate investment is one of the economic forces that encourages growth.

Theoretical Review

Agency Cost Theory

Berle and Means introduced agency cost theory decades ago in 1932. Berle and Means (1932), in their seminal work on the separation of ownership from firm management, claimed that principal-agent difficulties may arise. The principal-agent issue occurs when a person or organization's priorities differ from those of the representative authorised to act on their behalf. An agent may act against the principal's best interests. The link between corporate governance and book-tax difference provides an appealing incentive for companies to expand, because tax shelters allow taxpayers to conduct their financial transactions in such a way that they incur the least amount of tax burden. Management opportunism, also known as resource diversion, is another type of agency issue mentioned under avoidance (Desai & Dharmapala, 2007), which is caused by increased cash flow due to tax savings. From the agency's perspective, the Board's role as an internal governance mechanism for controlling and monitoring arose from the need for accountability created by the separation of ownership and control (Berle & Means, 1932 in Nicholson & Kiel, 2004) and increased corporate scandals and disasters (Zandstra, 2002). As a result, this theory provides insight into the board's governance obligation to prevent managerial self-dealing, neglect, and lack of professionalism in reacting to the corporation's business (Dallas, 2003).

Empirical Review

Igburu and Orife (2024) looked at the effect of tax evasion on firm value of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. 177 companies that are quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group are included in the study. Five companies made up the sample size. They employed secondary sources for data collection. The dependent variable is the firms' value as determined by Tobin Q, whereas the independent variable, tax avoidance was measured with deferred tax, tax credit, dividend distribution, and employee benefit. The study's hypotheses were put to the test using the correlation coefficient. The research findings indicate that there is no statistically significant effect of deferred tax on firm value, nor is there any significant effect of tax credits on firm value. Additionally, there is a statistically significant effect of employee benefits on firm value.

Delgado et al. (2023) used artificial neural network regressions to examine the relationship between tax avoidance and profit management in the five largest European Union economies (Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Italy, and Spain). They used a dataset from the CompStat database covering the years 2006 to 2015. The study's independent variables were the effective tax rate (split into GAAP and CASH tax rates) and book-tax disparities, whereas the dependent variable was discretionary accruals. The findings show nonlinear patterns and a positive, statistically significant relationship between discretionary accruals and both ETR indicators, implying that when companies use earnings management, they will have a higher taxable income, higher ETR, and less tax avoidance. The study also highlighted the fact that discretionary accruals do not appear to affect BTD.

Liu and Zhao (2022) assessed the challenges faced by investors in the mispricing of book-tax differences using China's fixed asset depreciation legislation issued in 2014. They obtained data from Shanghai and Shenzhen a-share listed firms from the CSMAR database from 2014 to 2019, with a sample of 561 observations for profits growth and 565 observations for investor pricing analysis. The main factors were future profit growth ($G_{i,t+1}$) and investor pricing ($R_{year,t+1}$), while overall temporary BTD (AccBTDD) and other temporary BTD (OthBTDD) were the study's independent variables. They include earnings management (EM) by the abnormal accruals calculated by the performance adjusted modified Jones model sorted by year and industry; firm size by the natural logarithm of the book value of total assets;

book-to-market ratio (BM) by the ratio of the book value of total assets to market value; financial leverage (Lev) by the ratio of the book value of debt to the book value of assets; dividend (Div), by the ratio of dividends to total assets; and age is the year since Data were analysed using a multiple regression model with Newey-West corrected standard errors. The study found a significant positive relationship between AccBTD and future profit growth, whereas OthBTD is negatively connected with future earnings growth.

In Portugal, Pereira et al. (2022) sought to determine if book-tax disparities continue to impair earning persistence in the age of information technology and strict compliance monitoring. They chose 421 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) between 2016 and 2020 to achieve this goal. The study also used book-tax differences, which recognise the existence of both taxable and deductible transitory differences. To test these assumptions, they ran economic regressions on panel data. The findings revealed that earning persistence decreases as deductible temporary differences increase, whereas taxable temporary differences had no statistically significant effect.

Gilang and Wahya (2022) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility on tax avoidance. Agency theory was used to explain the link between corporate social responsibility characteristics and tax aggression. The study employed a variety of panel data regression techniques: The findings indicate that corporate social responsibility has a negative and considerable impact on tax aggressiveness.

Okpala and Omaliko (2022) investigated the relationship between corporate governance systems and tax avoidance among publicly traded tax-aggressive firms in Nigeria. To explore the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and tax sheltering, corporate governance mechanisms were measured using CEO share ownership, directors' salaries, board independence, and board diligence, while tax sheltering was represented by the effective tax rate. The OLS regression model was used to develop the hypotheses that would lead the investigation, as well as to statistically test the parameter estimates. The findings show that corporate governance standards have a strong and positive relationship with the tax sheltering of listed tax aggressive firms in the country.

Oktavia and Susanto (2022) conducted an experiment to identify the variables influencing income persistence. The study evaluated five corporate metrics: operating cash flow, cash flow volatility, sales volatility, operating cycle, and book-tax difference. They selected 43 manufacturing enterprises listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) between 2016 and 2020. The data from these samples was analysed using a multiple regression technique. The findings show that the operational cycle has a statistically significant impact on earnings persistence, while operating cash flow, sales volatility, cash flow volatility, and the book-tax gap have no effect.

Khuong et al. (2020) conducted a similar study in Vietnam to determine the degree of link between tax avoidance and the performance of listed firms on two Vietnamese stock exchanges between 2010 and 2016. The study picked 125 publicly traded companies and used panel data generalised methods of the moment (GMM) for data analytics. Return on assets, return on equity, and Tobin's Q were used to measure performance, while tax avoidance was represented by the effective tax rate and book tax deferred. Firm size, sales growth rate, financial leverage, asset tangibility, and operating cash flow have been identified as firm-specific features. The results revealed that effective tax rate and book tax deferred have a statistically negative correlation with return on asset and return on equity, but a positive statistically significant association with Tobin's Q. Firm size, sales growth rate, financial leverage, and asset tangibility exhibited statistically non-significant connection with return on asset, return on equity, and Tobin's Q, whereas the relationship between operating cash flow was statistically significant.

Aondohemba et al. (2021) used pooled OLS regression to investigate the relationship between the corporate tax mix and the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) in Nigeria from 2014 to 2018. The target variable was the firm's net income as a measure of financial success, whereas the independent variables were corporate income tax (CIT), deferred tax (DTAX), and tax incentive (TINC). The findings revealed that the relationship between business income tax and net income of the chosen manufacturing firm was positive but significant, whereas the relationship between deferred tax and tax incentive and net income was non-significant.

chi2(2)	64.1700	-	51.2900	27.7100	7.0200	59.4100
<i>Prob>chi2</i>	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0299	0.0000
<i>Shapiro-Wilk W test (Prob>z)</i>	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.1 presents the summary statistics derived from the dataset. The “Overall” statistics are conventional descriptive measures computed from 220 observations covering twenty (20) listed financial firms in Nigeria. Key measures of central tendency, including the mean and median, were calculated for all variables. Although both statistics are sensitive to extreme values, the proximity between the mean and median across most variables—particularly the explanatory variables—suggests a high degree of uniformity in the performance of the sampled firms. This indicates that differences in firm size do not significantly influence their tax management performance and that the data do not exhibit substantial outliers. Furthermore, the standard deviation, which measures the dispersion of values around the mean, is relatively small for most variables. This implies that annual observations are closely clustered around their respective midpoints, reflecting consistency in the dataset. Normality tests were also conducted to assess whether the data follow a normal distribution. Skewness, which measures the degree of asymmetry in a probability distribution around its mean, was examined as part of this process. It indicates both the magnitude and direction of deviation from perfect symmetry.

Table also, presents the outcome of skewness/kurtosis tests and Shapiro-Wilk W' test conducted to determine whether or not the skewness and kurtosis of a variable are consistent with the normal distribution. The probabilities (*Pr(Skewness)* and *Pr(Kurtosis)*) of both skewness/kurtosis, in this case, equate to zero for all the entered variables and the joint probability (*Prob>chi2*) of all the variables also equates to zero.

Pairwise Correlations

The Pearson correlation coefficients measure the degree of relationship between the variable.

Table 4.2. Correlation Matrix with P-values involving 220 Observations

	<i>tie</i>	<i>lme</i>	<i>btd</i>	<i>ocf</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>lnfa</i>
<i>Tie</i>	1.0000					
<i>lme</i>	0.7190*	1.0000				
	0.0000					
<i>Btd</i>	0.0246	-0.0093	1.0000			
	0.7170	0.8910				
<i>Ocf</i>	-0.1923*	-0.0806	0.1076	1.0000		
	0.0042	0.2339	0.1115			
<i>Flvr</i>	-0.7467*	-0.6223*	-0.1350*	0.1403*	1.0000	
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0455	0.0376		
<i>Lnfa</i>	0.1695*	0.2247*	0.0208	-0.0612	-0.1225	1.0000
	0.0118	0.0008	0.7586	0.3662	0.0697	

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.2 portrays a significant relationship between predictor variable (permanent book tax difference, operating cash flows all deflated by total assets financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age and total investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. the permanent book tax difference and natural logarithm of firm age displayed a positive significant connection with total investment maintenance expenditure. On the hand, permanent book tax difference, financial leverage and the natural logarithm of firm age displayed a strong association with investment maintenance expenditure. Permanent book tax and the natural logarithm of firm age exhibited a strong positive relationship with investment expenditure.

Test for Model Mis – Specification

Table 4.5: Ramsey RESET Mis-specification Test

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of eps			
Ho: model has no omitted variables			
		tieta	imeta
F(3, 208)	=	18.01	18.57
Prob > F	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.5 presents the outcome of Ramsey Reset test used to ascertain if the comprehensive model is appropriately specified i.e over or under fitted. The reset test implies acceptance of the null hypothesis that the model has no omitted variables. The result of these test shows $F(3, 208) = 18.01$ & 18.57 with P-values (0.0000) which implies that the model is not over-specified. Alternatively, the result could be ascertained manually by truncating a few independent variables and estimating another regression and visual examination of the old and new (full) residuals for $F_{calc} < F(3, 208)$ using the formula.

$$F_{calc} = \frac{(R^2_{new} - R^2_{old}) / \text{number of new predictors}}{(1 - R^2_{new}) / (n - \text{number of betas in the new model})}$$

Test for Multi-collinearity

Multicollinearity is an unsteady condition of the regression model, estimates, and over-bloated standard errors for the coefficient (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). They further stated that it usually emanated from model specification, data collection methods, restrictions in the population and sample size, and the common trend of the regressors over time. The variance inflation factor measures the degree of the (strong) linear relationship between one predictor variable and one or more explanatory variables. As a rule of thumb, Montgomery and Peck (2007) suggested $5 < VIF < 10$. This implies that VIFs value between 1 and 5 is moderate but above 5 is severe.

Table 4.6: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Btd	10.58	0.000004
Flvr	1.21	0.825739
Lnfa	1.14	0.877631
Ocf	1.06	0.944081
Mean VIF		4.35

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

A test of multicollinearity was conducted using the variance inflation factor approach (VIF) as depicted in Table 4.6. In this instance, the explanatory variables have resultant variance inflation factors ranging between 1.06 and 10.58 and a mean VIF of $4.35 < 5.0$ for the comprehensive model. These results indicate the presence of severe multicollinearity problems connected to book tax difference deflated by the total assets moderate multicollinearity between the explanatory (independent) variable in the regression model which is acceptable.

Test for Serial Autocorrelation

Serial autocorrelation is the sktistical description of the extent to which values of the same variables correlate across different observations over time. In cross-sectional data, serial autocorrelation can also arise when the observations are correlated in some other aspect other than time across panels. Hence, conventional analyses such as the ordinary least square (OLS) regression that assume independence of observations are prone to autocorrelation problems. In statistics, the Durbin-Watson tests are usually employed to test for autocorrelation in a time series whereas the Wooldridge tests are commonly used to measure serial autocorrelation in cross-sectional panel data. The Durbin-Watson tests generate a test

statistic such that $0 < d < 4$. Values closer to 2 (the middle point) indicate minor autocorrelation, and values closer to 0 or 4 suggest larger positive or negative autocorrelation respectively.

Table 4.7: Wooldridge test (All-Inclusive Model)

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data			
Ho: no first-order autocorrelation			
F(1, 7)	=	93.064	1845.54
Prob > F	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Further, the Wooldridge tests of serial autocorrelation in panel data were carried out. The Wooldridge tests assumed a null hypothesis of no first-order autocorrelation. In this instance, Table 4.7 depicts the outcome of the test. The result reveals a non-significant p-value (Prob > F = 0.0000) which is less than 0.05 significant levels indicating that the panel data is not free from first-order autocorrelation. Hence, we upheld the alternative hypothesis. Nevertheless, it was resolved by conducting a regression model that adjusted for first-order autocorrelation (ar1).

Test for Heteroskedasticity in Panel Data

Table 4.8. Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test for Random effects

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)
Tieta	.0095529	.0977389
E	.0010871	.0329716
U	.0010849	.0329376
Test: Var(u) = 0		
		chibar2 (01) = 340.80
		Prob > chibar2 = 0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test doubles as the test for the presence of panel heteroskedasticity and test to facilitate the decision between the *Random Effects Model (REM)* and the *Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS)*. The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) test has the **null hypothesis that variances across entities are zero** which means no statistically significant difference across units (no panel effect). The decision rule is that if the Breusch Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) result is significant at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected. As depicted in table 4.8, the result of this test shows $chi^2(1) = 340.80$ and $Prob > chibar^2 = 0.0000$. The result shows the null hypothesis is rejected as it is strongly significant at the 5% level of significance, which implies that the random effect model is appropriate for the model estimation. Therefore, the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is better.

Fixed Effects Vs Random Effects Tests of Model Estimation

Table 4.9: Hausman Test of All-Inclusive Model Validity

Variable	(b) fe	(B) Re	(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
btd	-3.455404	4.031168	-7.486572	0.163525
ocf	0.0281372	0.0235908	0.0045464	0.030029
flvr	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	0.0844565	0.0059191
lnfa	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	-0.0158186	0.0040423

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
 B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2(8) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^(-1)](b-B) = 129.44

Prob>chi2 = 0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.9 facilitates a choice between the *Fixed Effects Model (FEM)* and the *Random Effects Model (REM)*. The Hausman test has the null hypothesis that the preferred model is fixed effects vs the alternative fixed effect. The Hausman test results show $chi^2(8) = 129.44$ and $Prob.>chi^2 = 0.0000$ which suggest that the fixed effect model is not appropriate therefore strengthens the decision that the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is the most appropriate model for the panel dataset.

Model Estimation

The random effect (RE) regression model assumes that the variation across entities is random and uncorrelated with the predictor or regressor included in the model.

The random-effects model equation is:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_k X_{it} + \alpha_i + u_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where: α_i ($i = 1 \dots 20$) is the unknown intercept for each entity (20 firm-specific intercepts), Y_{it} is the regressand (TIE), i = represents the firms (1- 20) and t is the time series (2012-2022), X_{it} represents the independent and control variables, β_k is the coefficients for independent and control variables, u_{it} is the Between-firms error term, and ε_{it} represents the Within-firms error term.

Table 4.10: Panel Regression Results of Tax Sheltering Indicators, Control Variables and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial firms in Nigeria

Regressors		Method	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect (Recommended Model)	PCSEs (Preferred Model)
btd	p-value		0.888	0.887	0.885	0.026*
	t-statistic		0.14	-0.14	0.14	2.23
	coefficient		6.463275	-3.455404	4.031168	11.60817
ocf	p-value		0.081	0.315	0.426	0.152
	t-statistic		-1.75	1.01	0.74	-1.43
	coefficient		-0.0886617	0.0281372	0.0235908	-0.113669
flvr	p-value		0.000*	0.001*	0.000*	0.000*
	t-statistic		-14.97	-3.36	-7.30	-18.51
	coefficient		-0.3049537	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	-1.652166
infa	p-value		0.11	0.062	0.979	0.000*
	t-statistic		1.61	-1.88	-0.03	6.19
	coefficient		0.0092339	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	.0102448
_cons	p-value		0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
	t-statistic		10.95	6.64	7.02	22.42
	Coefficient		0.2848017	0.2054517	0.2121882	.177882
R-Squared			57.67	0.2615	0.5479	0.3877
F-statistic (Prob)/ Wald chi2 (Prob)			35.93 (0.0000)	3.31(0.0015)	59.16 (0.0000)	38.06 (0.0000)
rho (fraction of variance due to u_i)				.87062491	.49943843	
Poolability Test (Breusch-Pagan LM)					340 (0.0000)	
Hausman test				129.44 (0.0000)		
Original Durbin-Watson statistic				2.04		
No of Observations = 220				Number of Firms = 20		

*Dependent Variable: KCE, significant at *1%, **5%, t-statistics*

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

We employed the *multiple regression, correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* to correct the positive first-order autocorrelation (ar1) as identified in the Wooldridge tests, multicollinearity as identified in the variance inflation factor and heteroskedasticity as indicated by the Breusch-Pagan test and Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test. The model also corrected the errors of variance due to differences across panels, that is, the intra-class correlation suggested by *rho (fraction of variance due to u_i)* in the *Fixed Effects (FE) .8706 and Random Effects (RE) .4494 Models*.

The results of the model estimation are presented in table 4.10. The summarized results aim to address the objectives of the study as captured in the model thus:

$$TIE = -0.1779 - 0.0026ETR + 11.6081BTD - 79.7061TBD - 7.9577PBD - 12.3341TS - 0.1136OCF - 0.1652FLVR + 0.0104LNAGE$$

$$R\text{-Squared} = 0.3877$$

$$F(Prob) = 38.06 (0.0000)$$

$$Prob > F = 0.0000$$

From the statistics above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.3877. In specific terms, it suggests that 38.77% of changes in total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressor (*book tax difference, operating cash flows, financial leverage, and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 38.06 and Prob. = 0.0000 is lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 38.77% explanatory power of the regressor is statistically significant in explaining changes in the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model.

Robustness Tests of the Model

Robustness tests were carried out using investment maintenance expenditure as the regressand.

Table 4.11: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) using Investment Maintenance Expenditure (IME) as the Regressand

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Btd	-0.621013	1.783506	0.35	0.728	-4.116620	2.874595
Ocf	0.001429	0.002398	0.60	0.551	-0.003270	0.006129
Flvr	-0.006772	0.002319	2.92	0.004	-0.011317	-0.002226
Lnfa	0.001651	0.000479	3.45	0.001	0.000712	0.002590
_cons	0.006274	0.001768	3.55	0.000	0.002808	0.009739

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

From the statistics table above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.2538. In specific terms, it suggests that 25.38% of changes in investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressor (*book tax difference, operating cash flows, financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 28.93 and Prob. = 0.0003 is lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 25.38% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4.12: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) of Tax Sheltering Indicators and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Btd	-0.449181	0.788712	-0.57	0.569	-1.995028	1.096666
Ocf	0.000485	0.001346	0.36	0.718	-0.002152	0.003123
Flvr	-0.005318	0.000762	-6.98	0.000	-0.006812	-0.003824
Lnfa	0.001312	0.000253	5.18	0.000	0.000816	0.001809
_cons	0.006238	0.000903	6.91	0.000	0.004469	0.008008

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

H₀₁: Book tax difference has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

According to Gujarati, Porter, and Gunasekar (2009), the decision rule involves accepting the alternate hypothesis (H₁) if the coefficient for the book tax difference (BTD) is either positive or negative, the modulus of the t-Statistic > 2.0 (i.e |t| > 2), and the P-value of the t-Statistic < 0.05 (i.e. |t| < 0.05). Otherwise, accept H₀ and reject H₁.

As presented in table 4.12, the *Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* was used to test the above-stated hypothesis. In respect of the coefficient (β), table 4.12 above indicates that a unit change in the book tax difference will increase corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria by -0.449150. Precisely, the book tax difference demonstrated a very weak negative effect on corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria with a p-value = 0.569. Since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.569, and t-statistic > |2| at -0.57, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that corporate investment expenditure does not respond significantly to changes in book tax difference of the listed financial firms in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis tested the book tax difference and corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The book tax difference measures the magnitude of the gap between the IFRS accounting income and taxable income. The outcome of this test revealed a non-significant effect of the book tax difference on corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms with coefficient (-0.44915), t-statistic (-0.57) and p-value: 0.569. Ideally, this variable constitutes a major segment of a company’s tax planning. It is crucial that good tax management practice align the pre-tax income and the taxable income, and the monitoring of the book tax gaps provide an insight to possible tax aggressive practice as well as tax evasion at the extreme. Hence, we expect no specific outcome, which means that the magnitude and the direction of the outcome will depend on whether the book tax gap increase or decrease has either a direct or inverse relationship with investment in non-current assets. In this case, the result revealed that connection between the difference in book tax difference and corporate investment expenditure is immaterial but in the negative direction. This implies that the financial firms’ difference in pre-tax income and taxable income does not boost investment in non-current assets in the listed financial firms.

The control variables of the study operating cash flows of total assets, financial leverage and the natural logarithm of firm age exerted varying levels of influence on the corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the operating cash flow ratio to total assets exhibited a non-significant effect on corporate investment expenditure with p-values [0.718]. This outcome is consistent with the findings of Ahnan and Murwaningsarim (2019) which found that operating cash flow has a positive non-significant effect on earnings persistence of firms. Financial leverage and natural logarithm

of firm age exhibited strong relationships with the corporate investment expenditure, that is, statistically significant results (p-values 0.000 & $0.000 < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the book tax difference could be used to boost business growth opportunities and expansion in the listed financial firms in Nigeria when practiced within the provisions of the law. The study therefore recommends that: The book tax difference should be monitored to ensure that the Gap does not widen significantly. Albeit insignificant the negative direction of the effect is a cause for concerns which must be mitigated by effective tax planning policies.

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